

**Nigerian Television Drama Programmes for Children:
A Life Size Puppet Use Advocacy.**

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Abstract

Observed inability of any indigenous Nigerian television drama production for children in achieving continental or international recognition till date has motivated this study. Investigating reasons that may be adduced for the success or failure of efforts in this medium since the inception of television in Nigeria is the problem of study. The purpose is to motivate improvement towards indigenous life size puppet productions and use for children television drama productions in Nigeria. The study aims at improving television broadcast for children through motivating craftsmanship in life size puppet design and creation on Nigerian television. Methodology in the study includes; literature review, participatory observation, screening of programmes and interviews. Some of the findings are: Domination of Nigerian children television belts by foreign productions for children, need for motivation, training and retraining for indigenous designers of children television programmes and life size puppet designers. The study therefore recommends amongst others, that the government through the television broadcast media, other collaborating firms and companies or individuals should start a children-programme hunt competition with an attractive prize for the winning producer, director and life size puppet designer(s); to encourage development in life size puppet use for indigenous Nigerian children programmes and competition with international trends.

Key words: Popularizing, Indigenous, Children, Television, Puppets.

Résumé

L'incapacité de toute production dramatique de télévision indigène nigériane pour les enfants à obtenir une reconnaissance continentale ou internationale à ce jour a motivé cette étude et les raisons qui pourraient expliquer le succès ou l'échec des efforts dans ce domaine depuis le début de la télévision au Nigeria sont le problème de cette étude; dans le but de motiver l'amélioration vers les productions de marionnettes de taille naturelle indigènes et leur utilisation pour les productions télévisuelles dramatiques pour enfants au Nigeria. L'étude vise à améliorer la diffusion de la télévision pour les enfants en motivant la production artisanale de la conception et la création des marionnettes de taille naturelle à la télévision nigériane. La méthodologie de l'étude comprend la revue de la littérature, l'observation participative, la sélection des programmes et interviews. Certains des résultats sont qu'il y a une domination de l'espace de télévision d'enfants nigériens par des productions étrangères pour les enfants. Il y a un besoin de la motivation, de la formation et du recyclage des créateurs indigènes de programmes de télévision pour enfants et de marionnettes de taille naturelle. L'étude recommande donc entre autres que: le gouvernement, par le biais des médias télévisés, d'autres sociétés synergiques et d'entreprises ou des individus, devrait lancer un concours de recherche de talents destiné aux

programmes pour enfants avec un prix attrayant pour le producteur, réalisateur et concepteur de marionnettes de taille naturelle gagnant afin d'encourager le développement et l'utilisation de marionnettes de taille naturelle pour les programmes indigènes destinés aux enfants nigériens et le concours de tendances internationales.

Mots-clés : Populariser, Indigènes, Enfants, Télévision, Marionnettes.

Introduction

For the purpose of clarity, we begin this study by defining what a life size puppet is and differentiate it from Mascot and Masquerade. Life size puppets are usually costumed representation of an animal, bird, plant, nature element or a human being that is worn and operated by one or more artists oddly as may be unexpected. The design and creation of life size puppets is in the domain of costume and make up arts while the use of the costumes in performance only is placed under the art of puppetry. The motivation and focus of this study is targeted at the design and creation perspectives of life size puppet costumes. Life size puppets are actually masquerades in all technical details; but because of their socio-educative purposes and most times comical gestures, they are known as life size puppets and are a style classification found in the study and practices of Costume design, Prosthetic makeup and Mask/masquerade design. It is also not worthy that the artist putting on a life size puppet is more popularly referred to as an actor rather than a puppeteer as should have been expected. A life size puppet can be argued to be a masquerade; because it covers the wearer completely and presents a dramatic character that is different from the wearer like other masked characters. But it is not classified as a masquerade; primarily because masquerades mostly have a religious, social or cultural identity, while life size puppets are social and educational in purpose and have a programme identity, usually on television; because their use is limited to children entertainment and as multi-media educational tools.

When they are built for identification with a club, fraternity or as a product symbol for advertising only then do they adopt the nomenclature or term 'Mascot' (e.g. Michelin tyre man mascot). In this format of utilization they serve the purpose of a totem and become a symbol of good luck for the club, fraternity or product. The term mascot may be applied to all objects, including; carvings on wood, life size puppets and even life animals such as dogs and horses that serve as totems and identity symbols of a club, association, fraternity or product. Life size puppet costumes built for mascots purposes and animated by a person or persons putting them are in the first instance life size puppets, but not all life size puppets can be referred to as mascots and this applies to all life size puppets used for children television programmes specifically, which is the focus of this study. For example; Barney in the Television programme "Barney and friends" is a life size puppet as defined by several authorities found in thesaurus, dictionaries and Wikipedia, to name a few, but the life size puppets that are common to American base ball teams as club symbols are mascots, because they are symbols of good luck and have no other function than to generate an image for the ball club represented, which makes them to serve as totems (good luck symbols).

Children are believed to be influenced by what they see and television programmes constitute a popular attraction for children. While several attempts at children television drama programmes have been made in Nigeria between 1975 and 2018, this study observes that, most of them appear to fail in holding the attention of the children long enough for

them to imbibe the moral and cultural values contained in many of these productions and this has resulted in indigenous television programmes for children not being able to compete favourably with international trends. An attempt is made in this research to associate the limited impact of many children television programmes designed by Nigerians to defects in costume, makeup designs, the quality of puppetry design sometimes employed and the near absence of indigenously created life size puppets. There is also a visible need, but failure to use life size puppets in some of these television programmes made for children, which is expected to aid the advancement of national cultural projection to Nigeria's children, using Nigerian television as a viable education platform.

The value of Television as a medium for screen broadcast can be found in its potential as tool for child education and particularly, educational foundation. A survey was done on children belts of some private, state and the national television companies operating in Nigeria, by a selected screening team and it became obvious that there was indeed a problem, as many nationally and internationally popular life size puppets like; Barney, Big Bird, Shrek, Mickey Mouse, Goo-fee, Donald Duck, etc, all of foreign origins dominated the Nigeria air waves, but no popular life size puppet found was of indigenous design or creation. This research was therefore further inspired by the logic that; if Nigerian children are to stop growing up with dependence on imported children screen productions, which may be imparting western values and morals; no matter how positive such foreign values may appear, then the Nigerian nation needs to recognise children television drama productions as a tool for cultural projection at critical formative stage of the child and a possible avenue for gradual articulated mental colonization of a nation and sincerely strive to improve the standards of our indigenous children productions for local television, cable television and home-video. This can be done by investing in the indigenous designing and creation of life size puppets sourced from our popular national folk tale characters such as ; The Tortoise, Turtle, Monkey, Ram, Cock, Squirrel, etc. It is against this background that this study has been motivated.

Problem of Research

Dominance of foreign life size puppets and cartoon animation programmes on Nigerian televisions is a problem, because it is imperative for "cultural imperialism" to impact the children of Nigeria from such dominance of children drama programmes designed in favour of foreign cultures on the long term (no matter how positive such cultures may be). Survey of private, state and the national television companies operating in Nigeria in this study, reveal many popular foreign life size puppet characters in children television drama programmes; most of which have been commercially mass produced and become regular guests at children parties and are also brands on pupils' lunch boxes and school bags. However, none of such popular life size puppets found was of indigenous origin. Indigenous design and creation of life size puppets in Nigeria and the subsequent value of harnessing the employment opportunities and income from such creations and designs have inspired this study. The problem of this research is therefore, a need for indigenous designs and creations of life size puppets and how they can be encouraged and the exposition of how that can be achievable in Nigerian.

Aim and Objectives of the Research

The aim of this research is to encourage the use of indigenous life size puppets designs for children television drama programmes in Nigeria and for the purpose of motivating indigenous children programmes competition with international trends. The objectives include:

- ❑ To identify efforts that have been made towards the development of indigenous life size puppet designs and creations for children television drama programmes in Nigeria.
- ❑ To outline challenges that have impeded such development for children programmes in Nigeria.

Theoretical Frame Work

The foundational theory of this study is, Herbert Schiller's "Cultural imperialism theory" (1969). Schiller appears to be in accord with the theory of Bertolt Brecht in his absurdist theatre; in which Brecht proposed the theatre as a place for education and teaching that can impact and change people's view on contact, using entertainment as the icing that makes it attractive to the audience and in the case of the television as a more recent outlet for theatre presentations, such as children drama programmes, the viewers who are the consumers of the product are expected to be impacted. According to Folkerts, and Lacy (2008, p.413)

Schiller sensitized readers to the implications of importing movies and other U.S. media products. He also put leading media companies on notice that Mickey Mouse in Borneo, no matter how endearing, had untoward implications for the indigenous culture. U.S. corporate greed, he said was undermining native cultures in developing countries. He described the process as insidious. People in developing countries found U.S. media products so slickly produced and packaged that, candy-like, they were irresistible no matter the destruction they were causing to the indigenous traditions and values that were fading into oblivion.

Herbert Schiller's cultural imperialism theory on its own is a reality of the teaching capability of the audio visual media which is supposed to be in contrast to Paul Lazarsfeld's "Minimalist effect theory" (1940), but is not because Lazarsfeld presents the media as having minimal effect on the public, but invariably still acknowledges television as a teacher. Schiller's theory however, is in agreement with Elisabeth Noelle Neumann's Cumulative effects theory (1973), which strongly suggests that the media is a slow but consistent teacher that can change the culture of a nation by consistently exposing the children of the victim culture to a foreign culture (good or bad) to the extent that children grow up with the new culture as theirs and jettison that of their place of birth over time.

Research Design

The research design of this study is developmental design, which encompasses observation, experience and participatory experimental designs: That involved screening of selected

programmes for selected children groups, and obtaining answers to set questions from the children while observing their reactions and impact of the screened programmes contents and designs on the one hand. Interview of some major television programmers and life size puppet designers were also undertaken, for the purpose of acquiring varying authority perspective to the research topic on the other hand.

Television Programmes Selection Process

Viewing of Children programme belts of major private, state and federal television stations was with the assistance of a selected team of twelve under graduate students emphasising children theatre, at the Lagos State University, Ojo, Lagos, in the month of February, 2010. Total number of children television drama productions viewed was fifty (50) only; which consisted of a minimum of five and a maximum of eight children television drama programmes per listed television channel, in the following order:

Selection of Television stations and programmes

Television Station	Acronym	Location(s)	Number of programmes selected	Percentage
Galaxy television	Galaxy TV	Ibadan	6 Programmes	12%
African Independent Television	AIT	Lagos and PHC	7 Programmes	14%
Silverbird Television	STV	Lagos and PHC	8 Programmes	16%
Channels Television	Channels	Lagos	6 Programmes	12%
Lagos State television	LTV	Lagos	5 Programmes	10%
Ogun State Television	OGTV	Abeokuta	6 Programmes	12%
Rivers State Television	RSTV	Lagos and PHC	5 Programmes	10%
Nigerian Television Authority	NTA	36 State capitals	7 Programmes	14%
Totals		36 Cities	50 Programmes	100%

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Programmes: Forty-nine (49) notable children drama productions drawn from eight television broadcast networks in Nigeria included indigenously produced: “Tales by Moonlight”, “Kiddies TV”, “Kunkulu and friends”, “Young Brains”, “KKB Show”, “Nnenna and Friends”, “Binta and Friends”, plus foreign productions such as; “Mickey Mouse”, “Banana Split”, “Wacky Races”, “Casper the Friendly Ghost”, “Sesame Street”, “Gods of Olympus”, “Shrek”, “Tinkerbelle”, “Sponge Bob”, “Sophia the 1st”, “Stingray”, “Mighty Mouse”, “Pinkie and Pekie”, “Tom and Jerry”, and “Barney and friends”, to name twenty one most prominent. The programme “Jappa and Biri Show” brought the forty-nine selected broadcast for children to a round figure of fifty. It was an outstanding programme that aired for only a month for undisclosed reasons, but had to be added to the research because it constitutes the greatest effort by the National television and was funded on a World Bank loan.

Fifty children programmes, including foreign programmes and those produced by Nigerians were viewed as part of research materials scouting and by the assessment of the screening team, most indigenously made productions and some foreign ones did not make the shortlist of ten top programmes on the ratio of a minimum of five indigenous and five foreign programmes, because they did not succeed in providing the 60% of the laid down terms of considerations for the screening, which lists as follows;

1. Use of appealing and effective life size puppets.
2. Quality and appropriate set design.
3. Appropriatecostuming and makeup.
4. Original and unique presentational style.
5. Premeditated and positive cultural educational contents.

Considerations for shortlisted ten programmes: To qualify for the selection process that followed the screening and be part of top ten, a programme was expected to have a minimum of three (3) qualities from the listed criteria above. The following programmes were shortlisted:

1. shortlisted **Foreign**programmes; - “Mickey Mouse”, “Sesame Street”, “Shrek”, “television Tabbies”, and “Barney and friends”.
2. Shortlisted **Indigenous** programmes:- “ KKB Show”, “Tales by Moonlight”, “Nnenna and friends”, “Kunkulu and friends”, “Young Brains”

The focus of this study is on programmes using life size l puppets worn or operated by people and fantasy makeup which are physical creations of costume artistes. The life size puppets Barney in “Barney and friends” and Big Fowl in “Sesame Street” in the programmes are selected. Cartoon animation production characters like “Mickey Mouse”, which are mentioned remain outside the focus of the study, but are still within this research population; firstly, because whereas they are computer generated by computer designers and cannot be classified as life size puppets productions, they still constitute 75% of the fifty productions screened for selection of samples in step I of the screening exercise;secondly for animated productions being in consideration for this study is because of the mass production of life size puppet costumes of these animated cartoon characters and the popular use of most of such cartoon life size puppets at children parties and primary school events within the country. Such animated productions with existing life size puppet costumes worn by actors, remain within the population of this study and one such production is among the last selected six (6) productions that were screened for children in the third and final phase of the screening exercise.

Outstanding amongst indigenous programmes selected were two children drama programmes: The first was titled “KKB Show” on Silverbird television; showing from 4pm to 6pm, Mondays to Fridays and 8:30am to 9:30am on Saturdays and *Sundays, which attracted the attention of the team.*The production which had children dressed as adults, in a detailed Nigerian setting, was designed to engaged in solving minor children problems with serious adult procedures. The research team mentioned above, discussed and considered the

named children drama programme as providing a motivating sample of positive cultural projection for the Nigerian Nation, which is an objective in this research. The technical quality, cultural content and projection of the “KKB Show” drama programme were so inspiring that it brought to light the reality of a need to sensitize more design practitioners of theatrical arts to the real value of originality in design and their constitutional role as ambassadors of culture. However this production was dropped from the list of research material by the second phase screening executed by a team of academic experts, because the programme did not use life size puppet or any form of masked characters and there was a need to minimise the choice of case studies to include only three indigenous and three foreign productions that use life size puppet.

The second outstanding indigenous children drama programme was titled, “Tales by Moonlight” and was found on the Nigerian Television Authority national network, showing from 4:30pm to 6:30pm, Mondays to Fridays and 7:30am to 8:30am on Saturdays and *Sundays*. “Tales by Moonlight” fulfilled all the expectations for a case study in this research except for the absence of preconceived life size puppets, which by our view would have been most effective in the programme. It however made elaborate use of masquerades and un-sustained (without fixed identity) naturalistic animal costumes that may be considered elements of attempts at use of life size puppet. Other programmes too numerous and irrelevant to list here, were also viewed and considered as lacking in one or more areas of production design aesthetics as found in the designs and creations of their set design, costume design, makeup design and properties designs. It was also noted through the programmes selection processes, that no current or rested Nigerian children television drama programme successfully popularised an indigenous life size puppet.

Review of Selected Children Television Drama Programmes in Nigeria

Tales by Moonlight: A Review; The longest running and most outstanding indigenous Nigerian production for children is titled; “Tales by Moonlight”, which was from the Nigerian Television Authority. The programme was based on the concept of old traditional moonlight story telling that was a major source of entertainment, transfer of oral literature and cultural education of the many ethnic groups found in Nigeria. Nwankwo (Interview) states that, what they did “...in “Tales by Moonlight” is to get these young ones to learn the values of our society and correct some misinformation to correct what they are doing wrong. Things that will give them a foundation to be better leaders tomorrow...” Onyedibia agrees with Nwankwo on the purpose of the programme, but he goes on to access its failures critically. According to Onyedibia (Interview):

‘Tales by Moonlight’ was exiting at that time but refused to develop technically with the times. There was a deficiency. If you can manage to find one of the copies and look critically, there was a deficiency in knowledge of the content. Monkey is like this, monkey is like that. The designer is lazy and does not know if it’s the species in Calabar or Congo, they just give you a monkey that is not monkish....You want to create an image, an understanding for children who understand things differently from adults....I am not being destructively critical of those who started “Tales by

Moonlight”, its’ just that they forgot they were producing for children and they keep it dragging for an hour and in the process they kill suspense and fantasy of the children....their attention span is short. The programme may have been popular but the programme did not succeed, that is why it did not cross our borders

“Tales by Moonlight” was outstanding, because it was one programme, which no matter its short comings, succeeded in projecting Nigerian cultural values and was a tool for finding cultural balance against the dominating in flow of foreign programmes, between 1978 and 2008. Mbachaga and Ukuma (2012, p.629) submit that:

Notably, culture is the total and distinctive way of life of a people or society. According to Raymond Williams, culture “is a distinctive way of life shaped by values, traditions, beliefs, material objects and lifestyles of ordinary people in their everyday existence” (82) Peter Berger (7) sees it as “The totality of man’s product”, both material and immaterial. He argues further that society itself is “nothing but part and parcel of non-material culture”.

Ibekwe (2012, p.249), has succeeded in giving a separating definition to culture and tradition. She comments that:

Culture and tradition are often used interchangeably but further researches have made it explicitly clear that “culture covers a broader perspective than tradition” (Ibekwe,2009)...Tradition finds its location within the domain of a given culture, citing Okafor and Emeka (2004) who state that, “as stipulated by the Federal Republic of Nigeria, culture includes both material and non-material aspects of people’s life, while material culture includes artefacts such as tools, weapon etc(and) non-material culture embraces, institutional, creative and philosophical matters which elaborately performing arts, ideas, belief, values, symbols, language and so on”.

Costuming in ‘Tales by Moonlight’ was mostly a show of dress culture from different ethnic nationalities of Nigeria in ancient times, as required by the story of each episode. The programme did not evolve and sustain any Life size puppets, despite the prevalence of the monkey and the Tortoise characters in most of the folk tales presented. In many early episodes the stories were not acted, but were told by the narrator and supported with paintings and drawings of the events in the story. In later productions, Spirits were often represented by actors dressed in white and made up with white chalk and in much later editions in 2006 to 2007 upwards to the resting of the programme in 2008; known traditional masquerades represented spirits and ancestors. Onyedibia, (2015, Interview) looks beyond the focus of costume and makeup and observes flaws in the packaging and delivery of the entire programme. He posits that:

...In “Tales by Moonlight”... You can’t be saying something is in the dark and it is coming out in day light. And they have the opportunity... They have the camera and the edit studio...So lighting, makeup, costume, even those telling the story had problems sitting like news casters.... In1975, the black and white television made a major domestic impact in Nigerian homes. “Tales by Moonlight” started about then. We saw nature in black and white to which we added colour in our minds.... Now the story teller on that programme sat in a place with his legs crossed....When the elders told those stories, they never crossed their legs. They came down to the level of the children and came down with an open mind, not that ‘I am an old man behaving like a child... but as a child with an older body’. States were they feel you are one with them. That is what we did not achieve in “Tales by Moonlight”. That is a major difference between it and foreign competitions like “Sesame Street” and “Barney...”

Jappa and BiriShow: -The second selected programme of this study presents Jappa (Tortoise) and Biri (Monkey) life size puppets, which appear to have been designed and created to fill this gap of a much needed national children television life size puppets, in the programme “Jappa and Biri Show”. This has been the most outstanding Nigerian Television attempt to introduce quality life size puppet of indigenous origin and it was designed and created by the NTA Educational Television Station at Teju-Osho, Lagos. On why the “Jappa and Biri show”, may have failed in making an expected strong impact on the Nigerian television network, despite upward of seventeen years since World Bank funding and the state of art equipment (second to none in Nigeria at 2002 when a facility tour was granted this researcher), the manager of NTA station in Port Harcourt, who was seconded from Lagos, Francisca Nwankwo,(Interview) confronted with the question of why this programme has not achieved regular broadcast or made any impact in the country till date in an interview, responds by saying;

...I cannot sit here and tell you this is the real situation, reason or position. I can’t say if it has failed or has not made an impact. The designers of the programme must have an objective, so for you to sit here and judge, you have to go and find out what their objective was first, for such a programme. Was it meant to be on air, or was it meant to be for training, or what? For you to talk, you need facts through research to defend your points.

Efforts to get the details and answers at the Educational Television studio for these possibilities raised by Nwankwo, proved most abortive, as access to information was denied us at the ETV studio. It is obvious to anyone living in Nigeria however that, in the last ten years the named production is yet to be made popular.

Picture 1&2: Jappa and Biri, Prototype masks. (Nwachuku, D., Designer, 2002)

(Both masks and their costumes were later reviewed for brighter colours by another designer [Aishatu] at the NTA educational Television Studio, Teju-Osho, Yaba, Lagos.)

Barney and Friends: - The Third programme of interest in this research is an American made television drama production for children titled “Barney and Friends”; Barney the principal Life size puppets in the production is a fantasy recreation of a Tyrannosaurus-Rex. A dinosaur believed by scientific findings to be the most carnivorous and vicious dinosaur that ever lived, is what has been imaginatively made peaceful and harmless by use of colour, texture of material and design cuts. Barney has a rounded mouth with blunt cubed teeth, but the real Tyrannosaurus-Rex (T-Rex) has pointed mighty mouth filled with spiked teeth. Barney is green with a purple under belly, while this dinosaur it represents is multi-shades of brown and black, the legs of T-Rex alone, up to the waist is more than Barneys’ entire height. T-Rex has a hard and rough body, but Barney is visibly soft and cuddly.

Picture 3: The life size puppets named Barney at play with children. (Video extract from the production, 2015

These are what make children want to embrace Barney; a product of a costume designer's imagination. Orokonwu, (2017, Interview) supports the above observations when he comments that:

Colour, animation of the figure created should be unusual and playful. Texture is also important; children must touch the life size puppets. I have one such life size puppet at the Rivers state carnival secretariat; it is a crocodile of about 5feet height. It is at the rivers state tourism board, on display at the entrance room to the Director General's office. Wish I could locate the Picture for you. You can also build life size puppet to be worn by children or static life size puppets on frames, with artificial animation.

Sesame Street: - The third production with a life size puppet of interest in this study is found in the programme "Sesame Street" which focuses on teaching elementary mathematics and English language. It also teaches Universal moral values and some degree of English culture. Big fowl of 'Sesame Street' as the key life size puppet in the named programme is a cross breed between a chicken and an Ostrich, with long golden Bick, fluffy golden chicken feathers, on a large 1.87 meter body of an Ostrich, interior of Bick is bright red and the legs are large, pink in colour with orange loops which terminates in flipper shaped feet.

Picture 4: Big Bird of Sesame Street. (Video extract from Sesame Street, 2015)

It is actually more of a life size Ostrich with very big white dreamy comic eyes. This puppet plays a combination of mother and teacher figure to the children who come to visit her in the programme.

Both programmes teach junior elementary mathematics, English language, Social Nature studies and. morals devoid of any religious under tone. The concept of a talking friendly Ostrich is fantasy. The details of the costume exaggerate the beak and make a ridicule of the scanty feather wings of an Ostrich by substituting it with that of a chicken. The contents of ‘Barney and friends’ and ‘Sesame Street’ are attempts at making education fun in a video-media approach and they do not appear to attempt projecting any particular national culture intentionally, but duel on universally acceptable values of education and the child. This universal culture outlook is the most outstanding reason for favouring these programmes for focus in this research. It is not surprising that Nigeria on a franchise adapted this programme and began airing it on the Nigerian Television Authority network in 2016. According to Boyle,A. (2017, Interview),

All (we) do is to rely on the foreign ones like: “Barney and Friends”, “Telly Toby’s” and the old one, “Sesame Street” which has been adapted to “Sesame Square” on the Nigerian Television Authority network, since 2016. Same costumes, same characters and puppets, only the children are Nigerians and the names have been Africanised. They foreign it and adapted it to the Nigerian situation and setting.

It is West Africa's first adaptation of "Sesame Street" and Africa's second of such an adaptation, with the first in South Africa as a nation.

The set in "Sesame Square" is a representation of an African village square with a huge mango tree in the centre. The programme presents Kami; the HIV positive puppet (first used in the South African version). The cookie monster is converted to Zobi, the yam monster. Major characters like the life size puppets; Big Bird, Bert and Ernie (human characters) are retained. All characters have been re-voiced to give them Nigerian accents, even the opening montage music now includes a talking drum and is a Nigerian popular folk song. This programme cannot be considered an indigenous effort, as it lacks originality. At most, the derogatory term "aping" of a foreign product maybe applied in referring to this "Sesame Square". According to Orokonwu (Interview),

Now, that is shameful. Why could we not develop our own life size puppets and puppet programme at half the cost, why did we have to borrow? They know what they should do but they have done this for selfish interest. Forex (foreign exchange) could be the reason for that betrayal. Another problem we have is late start to everything. When we do carnival and plan to execute even life size puppets in ten days. We need time to articulate, to analyse what we as professionals are going into and then find, cost and put together our personnel and materials by careful choices. But Nigerians wait for last minute and seek short cut to the detriment of the artistic creativity. That is why we buy readymade like the shameful "Sesame Square". Are we copying or trying to be who we are? It takes time and planning.

The indigenous Nigerian production for children, titled; "Tales by Moonlight" of the Nigerian Television Authority, was based on the concept of old traditional moonlight story telling that was a major source of entertainment, transfer of oral literature and multi-cultural education of the many ethnic groups found in Nigeria. Nwankwo (Interview) Further states that, what they did "...in "Tales by Moonlight" is to get these young ones to learn the values of our society and correct some misinformation's, to correct what they are doing wrong. Things that will give them a foundation to be better leaders tomorrow..." Onyedibia agrees with Nwankwo on the purpose of the programme, but he goes on to access its failures critically. According to Onyedibia (Interview),

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Still in attempt to capture the concept of culture, Ibekwe (2012, p.249), has succeeded in giving a separating definition to culture and tradition. She comments that,

Culture and tradition are often used interchangeably but further researches have made it explicitly clear that “culture covers a broader perspective than tradition” (Ibekwe,2009)...Tradition finds its location within the domain of a given culture, citing Okafor and Emeka (2004) who state that, “as stipulated by the Federal Republic of Nigeria, culture includes both material and non-material aspects of people’s life, while material culture includes artefacts such as tools, weapon etc(and) non-material culture embraces, institutional, creative and philosophical matters which elaborately performing arts, ideas, belief, values, symbols, language and so on”.

A major observation in this research on costume design is that, foreign children programmes in both computer animations and non-animation productions mostly appear to be a projection of the producing countries national flags in the choice of colours for the costume designs, particularly those produced in United States of America and Great Britain. For example; ‘Micky mouse’, ‘Daisy’, ‘Goofee’ and ‘Donald duck’, (all of Walt Disney creations) are costumed in colours extracts of the American flag. Marvel super hero comic productions of ‘Captain America’, ‘Wonder woman’ and ‘Superman’ are actually animated concepts of the American flag. In ‘Wacky races’ and ‘Casper the Friendly ghost’, the cartoon characters are not dressed in the British union jack, but in most episodes, have cause to make contact with the flag of Britain or England, or have the colours put on important property items in a suggestive manner. This is also the case in a few episodes of ‘Sesame Street’ and ‘Barney and friends’. The characters that use or project these flags are always virtuous and invincible or loving and kind. This is conceived to project the invincibility of the country projected and the spirit of good deeds and justice or knowledge and progress

represented by all of the characters mentioned above respectively.

Life size puppet attempts in children drama programmes on Nigerian Television.

The absence of a prominent television programme of Nigerian origin since the exit of The Nigerian Television authorities' broadcast of "Tales by Moonlight" is a problem that has become obvious. Although there are programmes on air, in both private and government owned stations, none has introduced and sustained a children programme that has become a national identity or archived an international appeal or export. The most outstanding Television attempt to introduce quality life size puppets has been the "Jappa and Biri Show" by the NTA Educational Television Station. On why the "Jappa and Biri Show" may have failed in making an expected strong impact on the NTA network, despite upward of eighteen years since World Bank funding and the state of art equipment, second to none in Nigeria at that time (2002), Nwankwo (2015, Interview) comments,

...I cannot seat here and tell you this is the real situation, reason or position. I can't say if it has failed or has not made an impact. The designers of the programme must have an objective, so for you to seat here and judge, you have to go and find out what their objective was first, for such a programme. Was it meant to be on air, or was it meant to be for training, or what? For you to talk, you need facts through research to defend your points.

Efforts to get the details and answers at the Educational Television studio for these questions raised by Nwankwo, proved most abortive, as access to information was declined at the ETv studio. It is obvious to anyone living in Nigeria however, that, in the last ten years the named production is yet to be made popular. It is also a fact that there is no popular children programme on the NTA, any of the state television stations or privately owned televisions, nor is there any popular private video production that has introduced a popular national Life size puppet in Nigeria made by Nigerians. This is a gap that is more significant than it may appear. There is an urgent need to evolve a television programme that shall introduce and popularise a national life size puppet for Nigeria, made by Nigerians.

From 2009 circa, the "Indomitable" cartoon animation by Indomie Company of Nigeria provided some cartoon figures of Nigerian origins and these cartoon characters have started appearing on children lunch boxes and school bags to the glory of Nigeria, but because the concept has failed in establishing an interesting television serial, it has faced unfair competition against such characters as "Ben 10", "Micky Mouse" and "Telly Toby's" (competing foreign animated cartoon characters). The Indomie Company's major means of reaching out to the children has been through magnetic cards packaged into the Indomie noodles products and comic pamphlets distributed as promotional materials by Indomie noodles staff. Nigeria as a nation needs to have indigenous cartoon animations and life size puppet programmes that promote our way of life and most immediately achievable is a life size puppet production for a programme that will be made popular on local television and must embody or represent Nigerian folk laws. Some of the possible popular folk law characters include: The Tortoise, Ram, Monkey, Crab, Cow, Grass Cutter, Antelope, Cock, etc.

Conclusions

Two issues of interests in this study upon which all findings and the recommendations are premised, are; improving content of television broadcast for children in Nigeria and secondly, encouraging the development of craftsmanship in costume and makeup design for children programmes on Nigerian television, toward design, creation and use of life size puppets. According to Nwadike (2006, p.150), “The objective of broadcasting is to reach a wide variety of distant audiences and introduce spontaneity in information dissemination...” The issue in contention is the creativity or non creativity of costume and makeup design artistes on children television programme belts. Ayodele, (2006, p.239) observes that,

Design is an art associated with craft. Design is the plan while craft is the way, through which the design plan is carried out. On its own, craft has been effectively defined as; “skill or ability in something, especially in handwork or the arts; proficiency’s expertness’. Design as a craft is a specialised or skilled study that has to do with proper handling of intended or design plan for theatrical consumption or for a better and relevant result...

Television and film appreciation requires a special kind of viewing, in which we should pay some attention to the techniques employed as well as to the entertainment or message contained there- in. The aesthetics of the design is a major tool of communication. While it may appear that this kind of divided attention will interfere with our emotional involvement with the viewed production, attentive viewing can actually deepen our appreciation. Design on its own, refers to the visual environment of a production, and costume alongside makeup are major factors towards the design resolution of a production. The creative capabilities of these two design specialties need to be resourceful, imaginative, focused on the category of intended viewership or audience and should in addition be well disposed to criticisms. Creativity is in the premise of imagination and fantasy is a high level of controlled imagination.

In Africa and Nigeria in particular, rich cultures abound. Most of our festivals involve life size puppets and masquerades, so the concept of life size puppets as a communal symbol is not imported to Nigeria and therefore gives cause for question on why Nigeria has not developed and popularised any indigenous life size puppet for children television programmes belt till date, at the least in the country or expectedly in the West African region in which Nigeria is internationally looked upon to lead. It is with a desire to contribute towards being able to meet this challenge as a nation of gifted people that this study was under taken and after careful review of all the variables found in this study, we may safely come to the following conclusions on the true state of things with regard to Television broadcast on the children belt in Nigeria;

- There is an absence of any popular indigenous life size puppet on Nigerian children television.
- Government and the Nigerian Television Authority are not doing enough towards using the children television belt for nation building.

- Foreign productions domination of Nigerian televisions children belts are suspected to have had serious influences on the national culture and need to be specifically researched to determine the extent of damage done and possible remedies, if any.
- Designers of costume and makeup for children television in Nigeria need training and retraining. The present structure for this training need to be updated.

Recommendations

Following the findings in this study, it is to end the serious shortage of popular made in Nigeria children programmes using life size puppet format and reverse a near absence of any popular children television life size puppet of Nigerian origin, by adopting the following possible remedies/recommendations:

1. The government through the state televisions or the Nigerian Television Authority, firms and private companies or individuals can start a children programmes hunt competition with an attractive prize for the winning Producer, Director and puppet designers as well as cartoon animators: The nature of the competitions should entail life size puppets being built and used on pilot productions by costume designers or prosthetic makeup designers. In the case of cartoon animations, these should be created by animation programmers and the winning programmes in the two format of life size puppets on the one hand and cartoon animations on the other, should be adopted and developed. It may also be of advantage if a third category for other forms of puppetry is considered to help promote puppetry designs. Ododo, (2000, p. 48) observes that, “The Nigerian society responds very warmly to the performing arts- theatre, music and dance. This stems from their orientation in traditional African theatre forms, which present a healthy artistic identity in their aural, kinaesthetic and composite forms.” It is notable that such a competition by a private effort on the art of dance, known as ‘Maltina Dance All’ helped place Nigeria in first position in 2009 amongst the nations of the world in dance, while creating wealth for winning families and changing the public view of a dancer; from an unserious person to a hard working celebrity. Two similar programmes on television that are titled; ‘Next movie Star’ and ‘Project Fame’ have similarly impacted Nigeria’s Nollywood and the music industry in the country respectively. These propositions of contests in the categories specified above are expected to do same for children television drama programmes designers and supporting artisans.

2. A second possible solution is for television programme planners to plan a quarter of the programmes for children with a firm resolve that one should be in life size puppets medium. This is one way of attracting theatre designers to television.

3. A third option is for gifted designers to embark on bold production of not just the costume and makeup designs, but complete programmes, from concept to production, then find a television or video outlet. Boyle shares this view when he recommends that, “we the children theatre experts, designers and creators of life size puppets can now begin to tell our Nigerian folk tales in the life size puppet format, to enable the television houses carry the story as we want it to be.” This is self reliance and calls for sacrifice. Production cost must be kept at a minimum, but the creative mind with confidence in his art must produce at the least a pilot of his idea before seeking a possible sponsor. Ododorecognises the poor funding and poor will of government towards funding the arts. According to Ododo, (2000, p.53),

Despite the fact that the Nigerian Cultural policy recommends the decentralization of cultural infrastructure like arts centres to reach the grassroots, no tangible achievement has been recorded in keeping with this recommendation. Similarly, the issue of funding the performing arts is still a dragging one. The Nigerian government is still waiting to be convinced why it should fund the performing arts despite its conspicuous presence in the cultural policy.

It is therefore the responsibility of the artist to stop waiting for this funding that may not come and recognise his art as a business that can be marketed to a profitable end.

To aid the development of the puppetry and animation arts, some deficiencies that need to be addressed are enumerated as follows: First is that a need for picture illustrations in publications and minimal efforts at same are a cause for concern; more efforts in publications towards demonstrative processes of costume and makeup building and applications are advocated by this study. Not many practitioners on the field can figure out how to actually achieve a described costume or makeup from theoretical instructions. Illustrations in pictures help other practitioners and students to understand the processes used and the quality of result realised by the one who is publishing. It has been observed by a survey of available illustrative books of foreign origins, that some processes for achieving desirable results in prosthetics makeup and pastiche arts (art of wig making); on Caucasians, do not achieve same results with Negros. The need is therefore strong for the development of local application techniques and demonstration on the usage of indigenous makeup and costume designs of African origins. It is however heart warming to note that some academics like Tracy Utoh-Ezeajugh (a Professor at the NnamdiAzikiwe University Awka, in Anambra state, of Nigeria) and few others have put some publications of the desired nature in circulation, particularly on the Uli makeup applications, kaolin and other related indigenous makeup materials and designs. Designers are encouraged to document their work in progress with pictures and explanatory graphics for the academia.

The next group of deficiencies needing urgent attention is a need for formal education for costume and makeup practitioners. Curriculum deficiencies in Universities and lack of sufficient practice contents in training programmes of institutions and apprentice masters as found in this study are some major factors responsible for insufficient researches towards design conceptualization and development, as observed amongst costume and makeup designers for children television programmes. The following recommendations should make a difference if implemented:

A. Lack of Specialists; Nigerian Universities should introduce practical test systems for interview and engagement of specialist staff and should endeavour to employ as well as train more specialists in costume, makeup and other technical theatre design arts.

B. Retraining of staff; Staff needs to be retrained to keep up to date on modern developments. This must not necessarily mean only sending the staff on courses and leaving a gap at their absence, workshops should be organised at least once per semester.

C. Curriculum Deficiencies; This study discovered a great effort to review curriculum in most universities for better performance and specialisation of the performing arts

from the year 2012 to 2017. However, some of the new curricular still do not emphasize practice in the design arts of the theatre as some hold on to too much theories of the design arts and little provision for practice. In addition, curricular reforms should separate the design arts of the theatre from other major art of the theatre, like artistic and management from theatrical designs and extend this to the separation of design arts specializations from each other. For example; it is out dated for Scenography (set design) to be combined with lighting design in this era, or for costume to be stuck to makeup, yet some theatres still combine all four design arts just mentioned as a single course, without pondering on the specialty of the would be lecturer of a course with such a multiple specialization. All of the named areas of theatre arts technical design specializations should independently be special areas in which students can emphasis or major and the lecturers would be more able to cover deeper theoretical details and run practical workshops, to the benefit of skill acquisition by students in the usually short and regularly disrupted semesters of Nigerian University system.

D. Lack of equipment; while some Universities lack infrastructure, despite Tertiary Institutions Trust Fund (TETFUND) efforts of the government. It is a proven fact that all Universities theatre arts units in Nigeria lack technical equipment; particularly for costume design, sound design, makeup design and special effects. This is a matter needing urgent attention. It was observed in most Universities visited in the course of this research that the professionals who will work with this equipment are kept aside when purchase orders are being placed. Items acquired are often technically obsolete, irrelevant or unfamiliar to the end user. The problem may be traced to corruption, bureaucracy, and poor maintenance culture. Items acquired are soon left to fall into disrepair, because the departments have no funding for maintenance and the works departments want to buy new equipment and make individual profit for themselves and the purchasing department; rather than maintain the existing equipment that are mostly serviceable. Items are stolen, personalised or made to disappear by students and staff in parts or whole. The Universities need to rethink their present contractor systems of purchasing basic teaching and laboratory equipment and better ways of protecting the equipment that are available from theft and wilful damage.

A third deficiency needing urgent attention is professional conducts and quality assurance in television stations in Nigeria. Nepotism, bribery, sex advances, and other vices need to be countered and hopefully reduced, through the use of agencies like the Professional Ethics Commission. But regrettably this proposition may not be tenable in the near future due to the depth and history of these practices, but efforts towards this should at the least be seen to have started. In the absence of true federalism in the political practices of the nation, tribalism and nepotism do not appear to be controllable vices, because Nigerians strongly uphold their ethnic nationality and view the federal nationality as a forced arrangement to which lip service should be rendered as a tool to accessing their share of a metaphorical national cake. Bribery and sex advances on their part, are international vices which thrive best in any society that lacks a check system for social vices, a nation where confirmed fraudsters are conferred with noble titles for stealing huge sums of money can only encourage more efforts into crime. Until the system learns to put checks in place to

query those who visibly live above their income, the so called war against economic crimes in Nigeria remains a political tool for political witches and wizards to deal with their enemies as appears to be the present situation

.Finally a gap found between the academia and the field practitioners of Film and Television, which bridging has been started at the University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria, as discussed earlier in this study is a positive development to the growth of both the artistic and technical specialties of the industries involved. This study therefore recommends that other universities, especially those with proximity with Film and television production centres such as the Universities at Ibadan, Lagos, Jos, Zaria and Nsukka should copy the University of Port Harcourt experience shamelessly, because it is a good thing to do. It is also recommended that Universities should urgently consider the creation of independent departments of Film and Television studies.

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